

Towards an open high-resolution land use dataset in Great Britain – Comparing and consolidating retail centre areas from open data sources

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Great Britain does not have a comprehensive and openly licenced high-resolution land use dataset that includes detail on building usage, but OpenStreetMap (OSM) has potential as a good base for creation of such a dataset [1]. OSM's quality and completeness is highly variable, but often good and improving, including for land use mapping [2,3]. This research evaluates use of separate open datasets to augment OSM for Great Britain. The research focuses on retail areas as these have recently been impacted both by internet shopping and the COVID pandemic [4].

This paper evaluates three generally openly available datasets showing retail centre extents across Great Britain, analysing each by areal footprint and, where available, premises counts. Firstly, the Consumer Data Research Centre (CDRC)'s Retail Centres Boundaries 2022 product, secondly non-domestic Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) geolocated with Unique Property Reference Numbers (UPRNs), filtered for retail categories, and finally OSM land use retail polygons on their own.

The CDRC has produced several "retail centres" products since its inception in 2014 [5,6]. The initial product was derived from English/Welsh Town Centres as defined in 2004 by a UK government department, to which kernel density estimation was applied [5]. This identified 1312 areas in total in England/Wales.

In 2017 the CDRC produced a new set of retail centre polygons, this time based on commercial data from the Local Data Company (LDC) [6]. The higher-resolution data, ground-truthed by the LDC, was aggregated using a DBSCAN.

In 2022, CDRC published a new version, based entirely on open data sources. For England/Wales, Valuation Office Agency (VOA) data was geocoded. For Scotland, a snapshot of OSM points and polygons using the *shop* key with any value, or *amenity* key with a set of relevant values, was used (this was also used where VOA data was missing in

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certain areas in England/Wales). OSM polygons with *landuse* key and *retail* value were used to improve the areal geometry of some of the resulting clusters [7]. This identified 6344 areas in Great Britain.

EPCs issued since 2008 in England/Wales have been published in tabular format as open data by the UK Government, and regularly updated. The devolved Scottish government has similarly published EPCs covering Scotland going back to 2013. Non-domestic EPCs cover various categories of buildings, including schools, prisons and hotels, and typically include data on floor area. They include UPRN references, which can then be combined with the National Statistics UPRN Lookup file to reveal the location, typically of the retail unit's building centroid or front entrance. For this evaluation, EPCs corresponding to UK planning classes A1/A2 (retail) and A3/A4/A5 (food outlets) were included.

By performing spatial operations in GIS software, clusters of EPCs can be used to crudely reveal the spatial extent, size (floor area) and unit count of retail areas (see Figure 1). Some caveats apply, for example EPCs listed for subsequently defunct retail units, units undergoing EPC assessments at different frequencies based on changes of tenant, and that the locations of each EPC's UPRN don't reflect the spatial extent of the unit or its building.

EPCs for Great Britain were obtained, cleaned and deduplicated, and their property type field was normalised and filtered to only include the aforementioned planning classes. 322425 EPCs were obtained using this method. Scotland had only 14600 (4.5%), compared with 8.4% of Great Britain's residential population. This could be due to pre-2013 data not being available, a cleaner upstream dataset with replaced units removed at source, and a less dynamic retail sector outside of very large cities like London and Birmingham, not present in Scotland.

QGIS was used to buffer the EPC points by 70m (reaching across typical building extents and roads) and dissolve the resulting polygons into areas of one or more EPC circles. A point-in-polygon operation was applied to count the number of EPCs in each polygon. Polygons with less than five EPCs, or less than 40000sqm, were excluded. 5877 polygons remained, including 298 in Scotland. Floor area is available but was not used in this simple analysis as it was considered that multiple-unit areas were more important to defining "retail centres" than single-tenant large warehouse stores, but is a possible future modification.

QGIS was also used to process the data directly from OSM (via the GeoFabrik service), with OSM retail land use polygons buffered by 50m (reaching across roads). Areas smaller than 40000sqm were removed. This left 5009 polygons, including 384 in Scotland.

Finally, the CDRC product was examined. This was used unmodified, with areal/unit cleaning and manual corrections having been applied during product creation, a threshold of ten retail units having been used for England/Wales (from the VOA data), which corresponds well with the five record threshold used for the EPC dataset because of the incomplete nature of the latter's source data. The CDRC product shows 6344 areas, 392 in Scotland.

Figure 1: Retail area data used in this study, superimposed on an OpenStreetMap map, in QGIS, for the Cowley Road area in Oxford, UK, showing potential for extension of the retail area defined in OpenStreetMap based on EPC data. Red line: 2004 “Town Centres” VOA/ONS data. Blue line: CDRC 2017 LDC data. Green lines: CDRC 2022 VOA data, H3 geography. Orange points: EPC locations for retail. Orange line: Buffered EPC locations for retail. Dark yellow: OpenStreetMap retail polygons. Light yellow: Buffered OSM retail polygons. Base map © OpenStreetMap contributors.

To determine the quality of each source, identify the most important missing data in the OSM land use data (OSMLU), and evaluate the EPC and CDRC product (CDRC2022) approaches, the polygons from each pair of sources were compared, on a “largest area in X not in Y” basis, using a QGIS “join attributes by location” spatial operation with an intersect geometric predicate and displaying unjoinable features.

The top five are presented, with observations with Google Street View imagery or OSM data to determine the reason for the omission. Where the area within a town/city is not named, the commercial centre is being referred to.

Largest EPC not in OSMLU: Edinburgh Old Town/Southside (*landuse* key missing), Bath (missing), Doncaster (shown as *commercial*), Burnley (missing), Dundee (shown as *residential*). Largest CDRC2022 not in OSMLU: Edinburgh Old Town/Southside, Cardiff (missing), Bath, Edinburgh Greenside (missing), Bishop Auckland (shown as *commercial*).

Largest OSMLU not in EPC: Edinburgh Fort Kinnard, Warrington Gemini, Edinburgh Straiton, Shrewsbury Harlescott, Guildford Slyfield. The first four are low-density retail parks, and the last is mistagged in OSM as an industrial/commercial estate with only a limited retail offering, mainly large car showrooms. Largest CDRC2022 not in EPC: Edinburgh Fort Kinnard, Newcastle Whitley Road, Warrington Gemini, Ashford Orbital, Edinburgh Pentland. All five of these are low density retail parks on the edge of their respective towns and cities. The EPC threshold of five stores and 70m buffer is too constraining to properly include “big box” retail parks.

Largest EPC not in CDRC2022: Kilmarnock, Greenock, Motherwell, Livingston, Bradford Greengates. The first four are all in Scotland, this suggests there are a lot of

missing buildings or retail points in the OSM data, as this was the principal data source for CDRC2022 in the absence of VOA data. Bradford Greengates is a relatively small and spatially dispersed retail centre on a major road, with the larger distances between units likely meaning the method will not have seen them forming a single retail area. Largest OSMLU not in CDRC2022: Livingston, Sutton Scotney, Bridgemere Garden World, Motherwell, Errol Sunday Market. Livingston and Motherwell are both missing the shop points in OSM that was used as the main data source for CDRC2022 for Scotland (In Motherwell's case, a contributor has subsequently added them). The other areas have the OSM retail *landuse* key covering much too large an area.

In conclusion, this analysis has shown there is considerable potential for the EPC data to help target improvements to the retail land use indication in OpenStreetMap for Great Britain, and potentially it could also help refine future iterations of the CDRC retail area product, as a supplementary data source. It also shows considerable promise as a more reliable base dataset for CDRC for defining retail areas in Scotland, as it avoids the variations in the way retail areas are currently presented in OSM.

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